

MIIX | MALAYSIA INVENTION & INNOVATION EXPO

Powered By DIGIT360 Sdn Bhd – UiTM Startup Company

3rd MALAYSIA INVENTION AND INNOVATION EXPO 2024 - ONLINE

<https://miix.my/>

<https://t.me/miixsupport>

miix22.secretariat@gmail.com

<https://registro.miix.my/>

<https://t.me/digit360hq>

What is MIIX?

Get the most out of our event. Featuring innovations from diverse fields and streams, MIIX is aiming to nurture the culture of innovation and design in the field of teaching and learning and other related fields among educators, students, and the public.

MIIX provides a prestigious platform for educators, librarians, students, and the public to participate and showcase their innovations and designs through a digital platform.

Organizer and Strategic Partners

Indonesian Strategic Partners

IYSA
Indonesian Young
Scientist Association

For Indonesian Participants,
you may contact the IYSA
representative:
+62 817-7091-4129

PARTICIPANTS

NETWORKING

Challenge your abilities with your peers!

LEARNING

Learn from experience of others.

EXPOSURE

Get rewards for your career advancement.

BEGINNER

Open to primary and secondary school students.

Age: 7 to 17/18 years

INTERMEDIATE

Open to university/College/Tertiary education students

SVM/DVM is eligible for this category

EXPERT

Open to academician, practitioners and professionals

BEGINNER

FOR INDIVIDUALS

50^{RM}

USD 50

- Primary School Students
- Secondary School Students
- eCertificate
- 1 x Medal
- Leader must be a student

REGISTER

EXPERT

FOR SMALL BUSINESS

150^{RM}

USD 100

- Academician
- Practitioners
- Industry
- eCertificate
- 1 x Medal

REGISTER

INTERMEDIATE

FOR MEDIUM BUSINESS

100^{RM}

USD 70

- Tertiary students
- SVM/DVM
- eCertificate
- 1 x Medal
- Leader must be a student

REGISTER

Virtual
MIIX | MALAYSIA INVENTION & INNOVATION EXPO **3rd edition**

Intermediate	Expert	Beginner
<p>100^{RM} USD 70</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Tertiary Students ✓ Leader must be a student ✓ Certificate to PhD ✓ e-certificate ✓ Medal 	<p>150^{RM} USD 100</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Academician ✓ Practitioners ✓ Industry ✓ Teacher ✓ Lecturer ✓ e-certificate ✓ Medal 	<p>50^{RM} USD 50</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Primary School Students ✓ Secondary School Students ✓ Leader MUST be a student ✗ PAJSK not provided ✓ e-certificate ✓ Medal

register at:

<https://registro.miix.my>

Deadline:

31st March 2024

Organized by:

MIIX | MALAYSIA INVENTION & INNOVATION EXPO

ONLINE EVENT

2024

MALAYSIA INVENTION & INNOVATION EXPO

SPECIAL OFFER

REGISTRATION AND PAYMENT DEADLINE

1 JAN 2024 - 31 MARCH 2024

JUDGING

APRIL 2024

AWARDS CEREMONY

MAY 2024

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REGISTRATION:

<https://registro.miix.my>

SUPPORT

<https://t.me/miixsupport>

WEB

<https://miix.my>

email: miix22.secretariat@gmail.com

Important Date

MIIX 2024 Important Date

RESULTS

May 2024

JUDGING

April 2024

REGISTRATION

1 January 2024 – 31 March 2024

<https://miix.my>

NUMBER OF MEMBERS

#RULES 1

Maximum of 8 members per project including teacher/advisors.

PROJECT LEADER

#RULES 2

Intermediate and beginner MUST BE LED by an active students. Failure to comply may resulted with disqualification of the participation.

VIDEO DURATION

#RULES 3

Presentation video should be within 4 minutes to a maximum of 6 minutes 30 seconds. Participant must introduce themselves in the opening of the presentation video.

YOUTUBE

#RULES 4

All video must be uploaded to your own YouTube Channel. Please set the video permission to either *Unlisted* or *Public*.

VIDEO VALIDITY

#RULES 5

Date of presentation video MUST BE WITHIN the duration of the event (December 2023 to 31st March 2024). Any video submitted with previous date will not be consider for the Best Video Award.

PAYMENT & RESULT

#RULES 6

All payment is non-refundable.
All result is non-negotiable.

MIIX2024 | How to Register

Project Registration Process

A step-by-step guide

Register using Registro Portal

<https://registro.miix.my>

Receive an automatic Letter of Acceptance through Registro Portal

Prepare presentation video and evidence (optional)

Upload video to YouTube and Get the Video ID:

Example:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gaxy2dyhMgA>

Copy the last ID only (i.e. gaxy2dyhMgA)

Complete payment through the Registro Portal

Update Video Detail (YouTube Video ID) and/or evidence link (Preferably Google Drive)

Virtual Booth URL will be provided

User is informed about their result

HOW TO REGISTER

Malaysia Invention and Innovation Expo

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Innovation and Creativity:

- The award-winning invention should showcase a high level of innovation and creativity. It should demonstrate a unique and inventive solution to a problem or a groundbreaking improvement upon existing technologies.

Significance and Impact:

- The invention should have significant potential for impact and contribute to advancements in its respective field or industry. It should address a critical need, solve a pressing problem, or offer substantial improvements over existing solutions.

Technical Excellence:

- The award recipient should demonstrate technical excellence in the development and implementation of the invention. The invention should showcase a deep understanding of the underlying principles and exhibit exceptional technical skill in its design, functionality, and operation.

Practical Applicability:

- The invention should have practical applicability and demonstrate the potential for real-world implementation. It should possess the necessary features, scalability, and adaptability to be effectively deployed in relevant contexts.

Market Potential and Commercial Viability:

- The award-winning invention should exhibit market potential and commercial viability. It should demonstrate potential demand, marketability, and feasibility for commercialization. Factors such as market analysis, business models, and potential partnerships or investment opportunities may be considered.

Scientific Rigor:

- The invention should be grounded in sound scientific principles and methodologies. It should demonstrate rigorous research, experimentation, and evidence-based approaches in its development and validation.

Intellectual Property Protection:

- The inventor should have taken appropriate measures to protect their intellectual property rights. Documentation and evidence of patent filings, copyrights, or other relevant intellectual property protection should be provided.

Presentation and Communication:

- The quality of the presentation and communication of the invention is crucial. The award recipient should effectively and compellingly communicate the value, impact, and potential of their invention through clear and engaging presentations, documentation, and visual aids.

Ethical Considerations:

- The invention should adhere to ethical standards and considerations. It should not involve any illegal or harmful activities and should align with principles of social responsibility and sustainability.

Originality and Uniqueness:

- The award-winning invention should exhibit originality and uniqueness. It should differentiate itself from existing solutions or demonstrate significant improvements upon previous inventions.

<https://miix.my>

1 Medal is given for each project

Additional medal is available for purchase at RM50/medal

MEDAL

Awarding Percentage

30% Gold **

40% Bronze **

30% Silver **

** Based on jury decision, originality of innovation and other rules and/or regulation.

** All decision is final. No appeal will be entertained.

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THANK YOU FOR YOUR INTEREST

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